

Design of Read, Write Separation based 6T SRAM Memory Array for Low Power IOT Applications

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Abstract: IOT based applications are nearly rule the entire embedded based machines and industries now a days. IOT based devices use lots and lots of memories to store multiple datum in the form of images, videos, audios and etc. Due to the capacitor is used in DRAM, which is more power consumed and uses large refreshing circuits. This problem is avoided in SRAM memory cell. Hence it's essential to possess energy- efficient present circuit static memory which focuses on optimizing delay and power. The olden days SRAM cell consumed more power and produces more delay. To decrease the power consumption and time, the introduced 6T SRAM cell separates read and write operation. The proposed SRAM array is designed using micro wind (45nm) and the power measured as 283mW, and delay is 20.5 nsec.

Keywords—low power SRAM, SRAM for IOT applications, low delay and power, read and write separation.

I. Introduction

Low power SRAMs have become a critical component of many VLSI chips. This is especially true for microprocessors, where the on-chip cache sizes are growing with each generation to bridge the increasing divergence in the speeds of the processor and the main memory. Due to the increased integration and operating speeds, power dissipation has become

an important consideration both as well as due to the explosive growth of battery operated appliances [1]. There are two purposes of an SRAM (Static Random Access Memory) design: First is to provide a direct interface with the CPU at speeds not attainable by DRAMs and second is to replace DRAMs in systems that require very low power consumption. In the first role, the SRAM serves as cache memory, interfacing between DRAMs and the CPU. The second driving force for SRAM technology is low power applications [2]. Research on very low threshold voltage and ultra-thin gate oxide are in progressive stage, due to reduction in the threshold voltage and the gate oxide thickness.

The phenomena like intrinsic parameter fluctuation, random dopant fluctuation, oxides thickness fluctuation, and line edge roughness further degrade the stability of SRAM cells. Large scale integration and fabrication process has resulted in increased density of devices by decreasing the device physical dimensions. Performance in terms of low power dissipation and high speed operation are the major challenges of integrated circuit design in deep submicron and nanoscale technologies. Designing high performance VLSI chip is becoming necessity for mobile communication and computing devices. Static Random Access Memories (SRAM) is read/write memory devices that can read data from or write data to any of its memory addresses. Static random access memories (SRAM) store data in flip-

flops, which retain data as long as the SRAM is powered up.

SRAM caches are the critical component of modern high performance digital systems and their dominance will increase further with the proliferation of intelligent systems. They occupy major portion of the chip area and contribute largely to its overall power consumption. Owing to the use of minimum sized transistors, SRAMs are highly susceptible to process variations [4]. The conventional 6T cell, which is currently the main workhorse of SRAM, poses several design challenges in ultra- scaled technology nodes [3]. Recently, with the proliferation in the demand of low power devices like wireless sensor nodes, implantable biomedical devices and other battery operated portable devices; power dissipation has become a key design constraint.

II. Literature Review

An improvement provided in SRAM depends on either of the three parameters or combination of transistor count, connection method and technology used. As VLSI suggests, the improvement expected should be in the form of reduction of power, area and delay. It can be done in 2 ways, (i) Reduction of one parameter without any changes in other 2 parameters or (ii) Reduction of two parameters with sacrificing changes occur in the other parameter. Various methods are already available to reduce area power and delay like, sleep transistor, tail transistor, power gate method, separation of read and write operations, conducting PMOS technique, less supply voltage method.

[1] In this paper, they used Cadence Virtuoso to perform an extensive investigation of the design of the 6T SRAM memory cells implemented in 45nm and 90nm cmos

technologies. Through the creation and examination of test circuits and schematics, the complex internal workings of the 6T SRAM were examined. When different input values were used, responses, including Transient, were produced. Furthermore, we meticulously calculated important characteristics like average power usage, area and circuit delay. there were significant variations in the 6T SRAM

performance between the three methods. In particular, the average power, area and latency in 45nm technology were better than those in 180nm and 90nm technology. 6T SRAM's layout was painstakingly created for 45nm and 90nm technology. Thorough rule checks and layout against schematic verifications were carried out, yielding insightful information on the Cadence tool.

[2] The proposed 10T SRAM has write energy and leakage power reduction of 89% and 96.6%, respectively while maintaining a similar read energy as compared to 9T SRAM. Additionally, a 4 Kb SRAM array based on 10T SRAM is implemented in 180-nm SCL technology to analyze the suggested IMC architecture. At 1.8 V, 60 MHz, the suggested IMC architecture achieves energy efficiency of 0.43 TOPS/W for 1-bit logic and 0.41TOPS/W for 1-bit addition. The area efficiency of 65.2% for a 136 32 array is achieved. The energy-efficient 10T SRAM bit cell with enhanced write stability is proposed for normal operation and InMemory Boolean based computation. The proposed 10T SRAM bit cell offers 40 % higher WSNM, 89% lesser write energy and 96.6% lower leakage power with nearly same RSNM when compare to 9T SRAM at 1.8V supply voltage. A 4Kb SRAM array based IMC architecture is fabricated by using SCL

180nm technology. At 60 MHz, the proposed IMC architecture is performed for arithmetic and logic operation.

[3] The proposed MTCMOS 8T SRAM cell is implemented, analyzed, verified and compared to the existing SRAM cells using Cadence Virtuoso with a channel length of 45 nm at a power supply of 500 mV. In proposed MTCMOS 8T SRAM cell, i) read stability RSVNM is increased by 5.89%, 5.72% and 4.74% ii) write stability WTV is increased by 4.16%, 4.16% and 5.05% iii) hold stability HSNM is increased by 0.24% iv) power consumption is decreased by 58.87%, 3.164% and 66.49% in comparison to conventional 6T, existing 8T and existing 9T SRAM cell respectively v) overall read path leakage current is reduced by 94.83% and 87.420%, when compared with existing 8T and existing 9T SRAM cell respectively.

[4] In this paper, we focus on power optimization analysis of different SRAM cells using transistor stacking technique. Using this stacking technique, instead of using single size transistor, we use two half size transistors. Here we connect the transistors in series which are turned off. This reduces the leakage current which in turn reduces the power consumption of SRAM cell. In this paper power consumption is analyzed for various SRAM cells with and without stacking technique using at different voltages are simulated using Hspice-A 2008.03 tool.

[5] In this paper, stability analysis of conventional 6-T SRAM cell and Schmitt trigger (ST) based 10-T SRAM cell with optimized sizing parameters has been performed and compared. The read stability,

write ability, delay and dissipated power have been investigated. By using N-curve methodology a significant improvement of 4.49%, 5.13% and 28.65% in SVNM, SINM and WTI respectively was observed for Schmitt trigger (ST) based 10-T SRAM cell as compared to optimized 6T SRAM cell. Furthermore, the effects of supply voltage and temperature on conventional 6T SRAM stability in read and

write operational mode have also been examined. Furthermore, both read delay and read current were investigated for ST based 10-T SRAM cell and found in desirable limits. It is also interesting to note that read delay is improved by 66%. Monte- Carlo simulation of the ST based 10-T SRAM cell circuit is carried out in order to find the deviation for power and the read current. The read current of the 10T topology is found to be 29.97 μ A with standard deviation of 4.55 μ A. Mean dynamic power for all process corners is also calculated by monte-carlo simulation of 4000 point each and deviation from the mean power was obtained. For simulation process 90nm technology node at 1V power supply was used on cadence virtuoso tool.

III Proposed Method

This project proposes an innovative method of improving the 6T SRAM circuit's performance by using Low-Voltage Transistors instead of conventional transistors and reduced the width of the transistors when compared to [4]. This modification's main goal is to maximize the circuit's write operations while utilizing Low- Voltage Transistors benefits, which include a lower threshold voltage and increased efficiency at lower power supply voltages. The write process has been thoroughly studied and modified to take advantage of the unique

advantages of LVT transistors and reducing the width of the transistors, with a focus on decreasing write latency, improving overall write power and reduce the area. The circuit's routing and layout have been methodically redesigned to accommodate the special qualities of LVT transistors, with an emphasis on reducing resistance and parasitic capacitance to improve overall performance. The suggested methodology is verified through micro wind software.

Fig:1 6T SRAM

Conventionally, elementary constituent of memory devices is Six Transistor (6T) SRAM cell as shown in Fig. 1. It involves two back to back connected inverters (M1, M3) and (M2, M4) forming a latch to keep the data intact. The access transistors M5 and M6 are utilized to achieve read and write operations. The access transistors are activated using word line connected with gate. Using common path i.e. (M5, M6) for read and write leads to conflicting situation in read stability and writability of the cell. For read process, the pulldown transistors and access transistors are responsible. Cell ratio $CR = W_{pd} / W_{ac}$ is defined as ratio of width of pull-down transistor to the width of access transistor. The RSNM is explained in terms of CR i.e. width of M1 w.r.t M5 and required to be kept high to uphold good read operation. While

the lower

pull-up ratio $CR = W_{pu} / W_{ac}$ is desirable to enhance writability of SRAM cell. However, if access transistor is strengthened beyond a certain limit to decline PR, it may result in destructive read also. Furthermore, during standby mode, to ensure maximum HSNM identical strength of pull up and pull-down transistors is required to set the trip point of both inverters at $V_{dd}/2$. Consequently, it is a challenge to propose some modification in bit cell topology to retain read stability and write ability while reducing the consumed power. This can be concluded from Eqn. that to reduce total power while read and write process, diminution of supply voltage becomes an essential condition. Though, scaling down supply voltage effects noise margins as well as delay in various process corners. Specifically, lower level voltage during read operation become difficult to maintain in SF process corner. This is because of higher strength of fast PMOS in contrast with slow NMOS with same size restraints. To settle the CR and PR values to maintain balance between read and write noise margins the width of transistors is enhanced. Conventionally pull-down transistors are kept strongest to improve conductivity while read cycle. But this also leads to increase in leakage current during standby mode. Threshold voltage of transistor also increases with increment in width due to inverse narrow width effect. Though, this increase in V_{th} is not adequate to contain the rise in leakage current.

IV Simulation Results and Analysis

In this paper the SRAM memory cell is designed for the 6T configuration in 45nm technologies using the micro wind. The graphs

Figure2: 6T Layout design in Microwind

show changes in a number of parameters, including delay calculations, power dissipation for the given supply voltage and transient analysis. As seen in Fig2, the results for the 6T SRAM are achieved utilizing 45nm with the given supply voltage. Figure 3 shows waveforms with a pulse width of 25 ns and a period of 50 ns, which are obtained by taking the values of VDC for $V_{DD}=1$ v, VPULSE for $BL=1$ v to 0 v, and $BL\ BAR=0$ v to 1 v. The term line ascends. The waveforms show Q and Q BAR as the output and PB, BL BAR, and WL as the input. Bit lines BL BAR and b must complement one another. The data are saved at Q and Q BAR, and the read or write operation is dependent upon the input supplied at BL and BL BAR. The application of the same procedure and its values in 45nm technology is shown in Fig3

Figure3: 6T Output wave form in Microwind

(a) Validation table

Ref. No.	technologies	Delay	Average Power
[1]	6 T SRAM 45 nm	22.7 nsec	294 mW
proposed Work	6 T SRAM 45 nm	20.5 nsec.	283mW

V. Conclusion

In this work, we used microwind to perform an extensive investigation of the design of the 6T SRAM memory cells implemented in 45nm cmos technologies. Through the creation and examination of test circuits and schematics, the complex internal workings of the 6T SRAM were examined. When different input values were used, responses, including Transient, were produced. This 6T SRAM design calculate delay 20.5 nsec and power 283mW.

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